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Objective of the deliverable

Clinical utility generally refers to the utility or usefulness of a finding, practice or technology for clinical or medical purposes. The objective of WP6 was to provide a map of clinical utility evidences for cancer and chart measures of evaluation.

Work performed – Results – Main achievements – Impact

Below you can find the PRS scoping paper as deliverable that describes the work, results, key findings and impact.

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Applicability, perspectives and perception of Polygenic-Risk Score in cancer within EU: a scoping review

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Abstract

The abstract serves both as a general introduction to the topic and as a brief, non-technical summary of the main results and their implications. Authors are advised to check the author instructions for the journal they are submitting to for word limits and if structural elements like subheadings, citations, or equations are permitted.

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1 Introduction

Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS) have emerged as a crucial tool in genetics, offering significant potential for enhancing the prediction, prevention, and treatment of various diseases, particularly cancer. Despite their promise, the clinical application of PRS raises numerous ethical, practical, and scientific challenges that must be meticulously addressed. This review systematically explores the ethical issues, communication strategies, and perspectives surrounding the clinical use of PRS, drawing from a broad base of normative literature and empirical studies. A systematic search of PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases yielded a comprehensive set of records, which were screened and analysed to identify key areas of concern.

Ethically, using PRS in clinical settings prompts a deep examination of its implications for health justice and equity. One major ethical concern is the potential for PRS to exacerbate existing health disparities, particularly due to their poor transferability across different ancestral groups. The reliance on PRS derived primarily from European populations means that individuals from other backgrounds, especially those of African descent, may receive less accurate risk assessments, further entrenching health inequalities. Additionally, there are significant concerns about the psychosocial impact of PRS on patients, including the potential for overtreatment, false reassurance, and the reinforcement of deterministic attitudes towards multifactorial diseases.

Effective communication of PRS information is paramount to successful clinical practice implementation. This review highlights the diverse perspectives on how PRS results are communicated to patients and the importance of clear, transparent, and culturally sensitive communication strategies. Studies have shown that while patients generally understand PRS conceptually, the interpretation and perceived value of these risk scores can vary widely. Therefore, healthcare providers need to be adequately trained to convey complex genetic information in a manner that is comprehensible and meaningful to patients, facilitating informed decision-making and personalized risk management.

The review also delves into the broader perspectives on the utility of PRS in preventive medicine and their integration into existing healthcare frameworks. PRS has the potential to refine screening protocols and guide therapeutic decisions, offering a more personalised approach to healthcare. However, their implementation is fraught with challenges, including the need for robust, diverse genetic data, and the development of best practices for their clinical use. The review underscores the necessity of ongoing research, education, and policy development to address these challenges and maximize the benefits of PRS for all populations.

In summary, the review provides a comprehensive analysis of the current landscape of PRS in clinical practice, identifying critical ethical, communicative, and practical issues that must be addressed to harness their full potential. It calls for a concerted effort from researchers, clinicians, and policymakers to ensure that PRS is used responsibly and equitably, ultimately enhancing its role in precision medicine and public health.

2 Methods

Topical subheadings are allowed. Authors must ensure that their Methods section includes adequate experimental and characterization data necessary for others in the field to reproduce their work. Authors are encouraged to include RIIIDs where appropriate.

Ethical approval declarations (only required where applicable) Any article reporting experiment/s carried out on (i) live vertebrate (or higher invertebrates), (ii) humans or (iii) human samples must include an unambiguous statement within the methods section that meets the following requirements:

1. Approval: a statement which confirms that all experimental protocols were approved by a named institutional and/or licensing committee. Please identify the approving body in the methods section
2. Accordance: a statement explicitly saying that the methods were carried out in accordance with the relevant guidelines and regulations
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If your manuscript includes potentially identifying patient/participant information, or if it describes human transplantation research, or if it reports results of a clinical trial then additional information will be required.

3 Results

3.1 Concerns: Ethical Reasons

In our work, we have explored the normative literature to identify the ethical issues related to the clinical use of PRS [1]. We followed the methodology of Stretch and Sofaer and the PRISMA reporting protocol for systematic reviews in biomedical sciences [2, 3]. After a systematic search of PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases, we screened 2209 records. Our inclusion criteria were finally met by 34 publications. A thematic analysis of the included records was subsequently performed. Our results were conceptualized and presented according to three areas of ethical interest and concern [1]. Here we provide a summary of key topics informing each section.

The first theme considers the potential harm of making polygenic risk information available in healthcare contexts to inform prediction, prevention, and treatment strategies in the context of complex multifactorial diseases. In most of the included papers it is argued that the interpretation of a classic PRS is an unprecedented challenge for a series of reasons. First, a PRS conveys only part of a patients' DNA-based susceptibility to conditions that are complex, thus depending on multiple genetic, environmental and lifestyle factors [4]. Second, a classic PRS is a relative measure that does not inform about a persons' absolute risk of developing a condition. Therefore, it is unclear what clinical conclusions can be derived, from a score, for a particular patient. Furthermore, while genetic risk is per se not susceptible to changes, a patient's PRS might fluctuate in time as statistical models are updated and new SNPs are included

in the protocols [5–7]. Interpretation failures and risk shifts are associated in the literature with iatrogenic harm such as overtreatment, overdiagnosis, false reassurance, and psychosocial harm [4, 7–9].

The second area of ethical concern regards the implications of PRS to matters of health justice. Most arguments in this area regard the poor transferability of PRS across ancestries, and its potential contribution to longstanding health disparities [10]. Other authors have also evaluated PRS from a public health ethics perspective, inviting the public to stay vigilant about key social and economic factors at the origin of common complex diseases, and institutions to take their responsibilities in this sense [11]. Given PRS current scientific limitations, traditional public health prevention strategies (e.g.: anti-smoking campaigns, initiatives to promote healthy lifestyles in public places) are still considered more effective and more just compared to risk stratification approaches targeting fewer high-risk individuals who can access genomic technologies [12, 13].

The third area of ethical interest responds to the fundamental question: what best practices could inform the prospective use of PRS in the clinic? It is acknowledged that PRS should inform a patients' overall risk assessment in a complementary fashion to avoid the above mentioned potential harms as well as the reinforcement of deterministic attitudes toward multifactorial diseases [8]. Appropriate risk communication will play an essential role in circumventing the risk of psychosocial harm and promoting the ethical use of PRS [7, 14, 15]. However, the establishment of best practices is still subordinated to 1) the closure of important educational gaps - both among health-care professionals and patients [4, 8, 16? , 17] 2) the gathering of both scientific and normative evidence on a series of ethically sensitive topics in genetic counseling, most importantly the testing of minors and the relevance of PRS results to blood relatives [4, 11, 18].

3.2 Concerns: Communication

Within the PRS/Concernings theme and Communication subtheme, our work involved a comprehensive search using keywords in major databases such as PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. This search yielded an initial pool of 911 papers. After a careful review of titles and abstracts, seven papers were found relevant to the subject. Communication was the primary focus across the seven identified studies, alongside other key topics. Analysis of the results led to the categorization of findings into five distinct sub-themes: communication, information, decision-making, education, and professionals' perspectives. These studies collectively revealed several critical insights and concerns, as well as a diverse range of perspectives on the complex interactions between communication and the related topics. Efficient communication plays a pivotal role in sharing knowledge about genetic testing and cancer risk assessment. The identified studies highlighted the importance of effective communication channels, ensuring that patients and healthcare providers understand the complexities of genetic information. [19] explored the communication of PRS in familial breast cancer settings. They found that consultations to provide breast cancer PRS were mainly clinician-driven and focused on biomedical information. Both genetic counselors and medical practitioners provided similar biomedical information; however, genetic counselors were more likely to employ

strategies to build patient rapport and utilize counseling techniques, underscoring their key role in facilitating effective communication in this context. Understanding how individuals integrate and respond to information provided by PRS is crucial for its effective integration into routine clinical care. [20] explored participants' responses to receiving PRS information and found that while participants understood PRS conceptually and accepted it as one of many risk factors, the value and meaning they ascribed to this risk estimate varied. [21] investigated women's experiences receiving personalized PRS and compared responses among women at different levels of polygenic risk. Regardless of risk level, participants demonstrated broad knowledge of polygenic information concepts and accurately described the implications of their PRS. Women's lived experiences with breast cancer informed their responses to their PRS, highlighting the importance of personal context in interpreting and integrating polygenic risk information into breast cancer risk management. [22] developed and pilot-tested a leaflet to assist women in deciding whether to learn results from genomic testing for common risk variants associated with breast cancer risk. The study showed participants found the leaflet useful, suggesting its utility as an information tool for women undergoing genomic testing. Communication is a critical factor influencing decision-making processes, as clear and transparent communication enables individuals to make informed choices about genetic testing and risk management strategies. One study highlighted the importance of integrating patients' perspectives in clinical practice concerning PRS and decision-making processes. [23] emphasized the importance of shared decision-making in using emerging technologies like PRS for cancer screening. Their findings suggest that involving patients in decision-making processes not only enhances patient-centered care but also leads to improved outcomes. Education emerged as a key component of communication, highlighting the importance of educational programs and decision aids in improving understanding and awareness among both patients and healthcare professionals. [24] demonstrated the positive impact of an online educational program on genetic healthcare providers' attitudes, confidence, knowledge, and preparedness regarding the use of PRS for breast and ovarian cancer risk assessments. These findings underscore the importance of continuous education and training initiatives for healthcare providers to effectively enhance their capacity to use PRS and personalized risk assessments. Finally, professionals' perspectives shed light on the challenges and opportunities of communication in risk-stratified screening, underscoring the need for continuous training and professional development to support effective communication practices in clinical settings. The study by [25] investigated General Practitioners' (GPs) views on risk-stratified screening, revealing both opportunities and challenges in its implementation. The study explored GPs' knowledge of risk-stratified screening, attitudes towards it, and preferences for continuing professional development. Results of the study suggest limited GPs' knowledge of PRS and risk-stratified screening. Despite GPs' hesitation and doubts in adopting a low-risk screening pathway, they showed optimism about its potential impact. Training, preferably in online learning formats, emerged as the top priority for future implementation. This underscores the importance of ongoing education and professional development opportunities to fill knowledge gaps and prepare healthcare professionals adequately to incorporate risk-stratified screening into their practice. In summary, these findings

stress the central role of communication in genetic testing and cancer risk assessment, highlighting the need for comprehensive communication strategies to optimize patient outcomes and healthcare delivery. However, there is a concern regarding how polygenic risk information is currently communicated and understood by patients. As referred by [21], future research should investigate this gap, focusing on how people respond to personalized risk information and its impact on health behavior, risk perceptions, and population-based screening. Such studies should include persons with an intermediate PRS, as this group represents the majority of the population and may have communication needs that are not yet adequately addressed.

3.3 Perspectives

In the PRS/Concernings theme and Perspectives subtheme research, a thorough exploration utilizing keywords in PubMed yielded an initial pool of 506 papers. After meticulous screening based on title and abstract, 11 papers emerged as pertinent to the subject matter. These studies shed light on several critical findings.

PRS have a wide range of applications. Their usefulness is mostly envisaged in preventive medicine, but they can also support therapeutic decisions or guide patient follow-up [26]. In preventive medicine, they could stratify individual patients as well as entire population cohorts according to their risk of developing a certain disorder and, as such, determine the optimal screening policy [4, 26]. For example, in many countries breast cancer screening is performed by mammography in women once a certain age threshold is met [25, 27, 28]. PRS scores could help refine the subgroup of women who would benefit from medical imaging at an earlier age [4, 25, 29]. On the other hand, once a diagnosis of breast cancer is made, the individual PRS score could facilitate therapeutic decisions such as mastectomy or more intensive chemotherapy regimens [4, 27].

While PRS are a promising tool to help predict disease at early stages, their application in clinical practice is not without challenges. These challenges, which need to be addressed for successful implementation, include accuracy in different ethnicities, selection complexity, and translation into clear clinical actions and patient benefits.

Firstly, PRS are typically trained on GWAS data from European populations, and it is unclear how accurate their performance is in other ethnicities [4, 26–28, 30–32]. Although many initiatives are being taken to correct this bias, progression is slow [4, 33]. Especially for people of African ancestry genomic reference databases are scarce [4, 32]. This lack of appropriate genetic data is problematic in low-income countries and high-income countries where ethnic minorities risk inaccurate PRS results due to an unfit reference genome application [4]. Biobanks should, therefore, increase their efforts to collect data of diverse origins.

A second limitation is the increasing amount of available PRS scores with only slightly different parameters, which often complicates appropriate PRS selection [26]. This was also reflected in a recent study evaluating the readiness of general practitioners to include PRS in their patient evaluations [25]. The clinicians report their need for more training as the top priority.

Translating PRS into clear clinical actions and patient benefits is also a significant hurdle to implementing PRS in health settings [4, 26]. Knowing one’s lifelong risk of

developing a disorder is only useful in case specific steps can be taken to improve health outcomes. Clinical trials evaluating PRS in real-life settings are urgently needed.

Moreover, integrating PRS with other data sources for risk prediction needs to be studied in more detail [4, 26, 28]. In some cases, PRS provide a clear additional benefit to existing stratification methods, but the impact may differ for each PRS and each disorder [4, 31]. Environmental exposure, age and socio-economic parameters are also likely to influence the genetic risk score throughout the patient lifespan [4, 27]. Artificial intelligence will be needed to generate PRS data and combine it with information from public health records [26].

Finally, the ethical and social implications of implementing PRS on a wide scale cannot be overlooked [4, 26]. These include cost-benefit considerations, reimbursement and insurance issues, and the impact of knowing one's individual risk for specific disorders [4, 26, 27, 34]. It is crucial to remember that genetic predisposition does not equal disease development [4, 27]. Due to this knowledge, increased public anxiety can be expected [27]. If more screening interventions are installed in people with higher PRS, this will likely result in more false positive tests, burdening them even further [4]. It is therefore of utmost importance to provide education both to patients and caregivers about the meaning and limitations of PRS-based genetic risk calculation. Health professionals should also be trained to counsel patients and their families, so they have a clear understanding of their risk, and to ensure proper follow-up. Patients should also be made aware of their right to decline these types of genetic testing. Informed consent is of vital importance in these situations.

3.4 Analytics: Model

In the realm of PRS theme and Model subtheme research, a thorough exploration utilizing keywords in PubMed, Scopus, WebOfScience and Embase yielded an initial pool of 40 papers. After meticulous screening based on title and abstract, 10 papers emerged as pertinent to the subject matter. Moreover, other 8 studies were found relevant by analyzing the literature on other subthemes. These studies shed light on several critical findings.

The previous years have shown a rise in the development and enhancement of models computing risk scores; in our review, we found several novel methods for Polygenic Risk Scores (PRS) In particular, novel penalized regression proposed [35]. ALL-Sum, [35] combines a summary statistic-based on penalized regression algorithm with ensemble steps for improved prediction performance, and outperformed alternatives in terms of runtime, and memory usage. It. Moreover, another method extending LASSO-based framework to create PRS used the Truncated Lasso Penalty (TLP) together with an elastic net, showing improved predictive accuracy [36]. Also, a model-free alternative is the non-parametric shrinkage (NPS) method [37], that does not require explicit modeling of genetic architecture. All the mentioned method claimed accuracy and prediction improvements with respect to canonical penalized algorithm.

Gradient boosting was also used in multiple studies [38, 39], in particular on breast cancer and prostate cancer. For breast cancer, extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost) was used to identify novel features for post-menopausal breast cancer, demonstrating higher accuracy in the augmented Cox model. Other studies intervened more directly

on the PRS algorithm, as for BRECARDA [40], a novel framework utilizing artificial intelligence neural networks, introduced for personalized breast cancer risk assessment. It combines a polygenic risk score (PRS) enhanced by AnnoPred with non-genetic risk factors. Another study [41] focused on integrating PRS from other diseases and replace the simple regression with a more in-depth machine learning method. In the era of big data, the combination of information coming from different studies is a crucial problem; In a recent work, the authors [42] show that for large sample size, it is often more convenient to linear combine the PRSs (Meta-PRS) calculated in each study, than to do a meta-analysis of GWAS summary statistics (meta-GWAS). The aforementioned methods achieve high accuracy and outperform existing PRS methods. Moreover, EB-PRS [43] proposes to utilize external information, as the distribution of the effect sizes, to improve the PRS classification. PRS as a concept by itself may not be a sufficient method; recently research states that the best performance, especially in breast cancer, are obtained by combining PRS and other risk factor, such as predisposition genes, and family history [44]; moreover, it is also beneficial to combine PRS with standard risk factors and mammographic density [45]. Recent methods have also proposed a non-negative matrix factorization method to better identify the hits SNPs, prior to their inclusion in the PRS model [46]. While PRS has been develop with genetic data in mind, there are recent developments to extend the concept for different data types; remarkably, Transcriptional risk score (TRS) [47] is based on multiple omics data to estimate the risk of breast cancer. Another method uses scRNA and spatial transcriptomics to build tumor progress-related gene risk score (TPRGRS) [48]. Using blood and urine markers, biomarker risk scores (BMRS) for common diseases without DNA information proved effective. Finally, recent work also highlighted microbe-based risk score (MRS) [49].

3.5 Analytics: Design

In the realm of PRS theme and Design subtheme research, a thorough exploration utilizing keywords in PubMed, Scopus, WebOfScience and Embase yielded an initial pool of 300 papers. After meticulous screening based on title and abstract, 82 papers emerged as pertinent to the subject matter. These studies shed light on several critical findings.

The evolution of design in polygenic risk scores (PRS) reflects an interdisciplinary confluence of enhanced statistical models, combination of multiple omics and/or data sources, and bioinformatics, culminating in advanced predictive tools for a range of diseases.

PRS was developed to assess risk combining multiple genetic variants. However, the PRS concept can be easily applied to other data structures and omics. In particular, there has been multiple applications on transcriptomics data [50–53]. Those studies involve different structures and outcome, such as transcriptomics transcription factors [51]; or the development of tPRS (transcript Risk score) for sleep disorder [54], or the analysis of a risk score on liquid—liquid phase separation or the assessment of chemotherapy benefit [53]. However, similarly to the canonical PRS computed on genomic data, also PRS on transcriptomics benefit from adding environmental and clinical factors [55]. Other factors that improve the prediction are the inclusion of

rare genes [56], or taking into consideration the gene’s interaction [57, 58] to extract candidate hits. Moreover, combining multiple omics enhances the risk assessment [59].

The integration of single-cell RNA sequencing (scRNA-seq) with bulk RNA sequencing enriches multi-locus risk assessment by providing a nuanced understanding of the genetic landscape at both the individual cell and population levels [60, 61]. scRNA can also be combined with spatial transcriptomics to build tumor progress-related risk scores (TPRGRS) [39]. Other relevant risk analysis are performed on DNA Methylations, to analyse alcohol consumption [62] or via Microbiome data [49]. Finally, risk scores calculated for a certain disease have been proved to be useful also for phenotypes with a comorbidity [63, 64] such when modelling different types of cancer or among psychiatric disorders.

A key evolution in PRS design is the progression from reliance on SNPs only to more elaborate frameworks, combining information from different sources and accounting for multiple factors, as multiple omics and environmental factors [65–67]. Such multi-source designs represent an improvement on previous settings that only used one single source. As such, family history and genetic hits complement themselves [68]. Other non-genetic information that enhances PRS are ATM pathogenic variant [69], individual clinical variables, body mass index and height [70, 71]. Overall, combining clinical and genetic risk score improves the predictions [72], paving the way for a complementary environmental risk score [73].

Single omics analysis only analyses a specific aspect of the involved process, and thus, combining multiple omics would be a preferred approach. Novel approaches combine DNA methylation with genetic variants [74] or with gene expression data [75] to create robust risk scores. Another feature proved to have a relevant impact is tumour mutational burden (TMB), the total number of somatic mutations in the tumour [76]. Combining PRS with metabolomics risk score [77], microbial risk score [49] and, in general, a phenomic systematic approach [73] have proved beneficial. Moreover, there is ongoing research on the best way to exploit genomic data; weighted PRS have been proven to be better than unweighted [78]; rare variants are often discarded in preprocessing steps in PRS analysis, but recent studies have integrated them into the PRS pipeline, showing beneficial effects in Prostate cancer [79], but a lack of improvement for obesity [79]. Moreover, functional PRS (obtained through functional SNP annotations) has proved to outperform canonical PRS in a Gastric cancer Chinese cohort [80], while also biological-pathways-bases PRS are introduced [81].

The adoption of novel techniques, predominantly machine learning algorithms, represents a significant methodological advancement that has enriched the predictive capabilities of PRS models. In detail, gradient boosting models have performed better than linear equivalents [38, 59], and a novel study introduces a genetic algorithm-based support vector machine [51]. Another promising approach is to perform a more tailored analysis for individuals with the disease but low-risk score [82].

Moreover, combining different PRS (meta PRS) also leads to better predictions. There is a potential to combine PRS for different, possible comorbidity diseases, such as different cancer types, to predict the risk of developing the target disease [82]; recent studies worked on the transferability of the PRS [64, 83–85], such as cross-traits PRS

for psychiatric diseases [83], or applying PRS calculated in non-transplanted to the transplanted [85], or transferring PRS calculated to predict circadian clock to obesity [84].

The advancements in PRS design hold transformative potential for disease prognosis and patient management. Incorporating into the experiment design a broad spectrum of genomic, transcriptomics and other types of omics, the predictive accuracy of PRS models is significantly enhanced. Cross-ancestry analyses, machine learning algorithms, and the integration of environmental factors represent pivotal strides in this domain. These evolutions contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the genetic basis of diseases, ultimately leading towards precision medicine where risk scores can inform personalized treatment plans.

3.6 Translation

The transferability of PRS across ancestries needs careful evaluation by cancer and ancestry groups since the effects have been proven to vary [86]. Approximately 80 per cent of all GWAS have been performed with individuals of European ancestry, who account for a minority of the world’s population. This can generate inequity, given that PRS are increasingly suggested to help inform personalized medicine and treatment decisions. Assessing the portability of PRS across ancestries is crucial if genetic risk stratification at the clinical level is to be implemented in populations with ancestry profiles that differ from those assessed in GWAS [32]. As SNP-based heritability is a function of allele frequency, loci important to disease risks in one population don’t necessarily contribute much to SNP-based heritability in other populations. The predictive power of PRS relies on the accurate estimation of allelic effect sizes and genetic similarity between training and target cohorts, where causal effects are captured by tagging effects due to linkage [87].

Poor trans-ancestry portability of polygenic risk scores is thought to be attributed to various reasons: (a) differences in single nucleotide polymorphism allele frequencies (genetic drift, local adaptation, genetic hitchhiking) and linkage disequilibrium patterns between ancestries; (b) confounding due to population stratification in the GWAS; and (c) differences in the true genetic architectures of disease, including gene-environment interactions and epistatic effects ([10, 88–90]. Additional factors may contribute to the observed differences in PRS performance: genotype data comes from arrays (*i.e.*, SNP ascertainment bias exists); imputation accuracy varies across populations, and the use of proxy variants can reduce the effectiveness of each PRS; clinical diagnosis of cases can differ across study sites; the studies used to generate each PRS have different sample sizes, and this affects the weightings of individual PRS variants[91]. GWAS favour the discovery of common genetic variants in the study population. The consequences of different populations having these population-specific parameters ultimately lead to differences in variant effects and overall PRS performance.

Ancestry-matched risk scores have been demonstrated to outperform risk scores that are not ancestry-matched (*e.g.*, [91]). In a scoping review of portability of polygenic risk scores in common cancers published in detail elsewhere (**Vaht *et al*, manuscript in preparation**), we found that the PRSs for breast cancer transfer

well across European populations and to Latinas, and, to a lesser extent, Ashkenazi Jewish, South American and South and East Asian populations but much more poorly to individuals of African ancestry [32, 92–99]. The performance of PRS for prostate cancer trained in European samples is relatively diminished in men of African ancestry, compared to performance in men of European or East or South Asian ancestry [32, 86, 91, 100, 101]. In general, transferability assessments of PRS models for different types of cancer have revealed that PRS models trained on individuals of European ancestry have somewhat lower predictive performance for individuals of Asian ancestry and significantly poorer performance for African ancestry groups. PRSs built from European GWAS are likely inadequate for direct application in non-European populations and perpetuate existing health disparities.

Unless well-powered GWASs are undertaken in diverse populations, the accuracy and utility of PRS will be sub-optimal, exacerbating disparities in risk prediction and subsequent disease management. It is recommended that PRS be constructed using GWAS based on the same ancestry group if large, diverse GWASs and their summary statistics are available. Larger sample sizes and greater diversity improve PRS accuracy. This will allow for a more thorough understanding of the development of specific cancers across populations and the development of polygenic risk models that can be applied across all populations.

3.7 Economic Evaluation

In the realm of PRS/Implementation theme and Economic Evaluation subtheme research, a thorough exploration utilizing keywords in Pubmed and Scopus yielded an initial pool of 27 papers. After meticulous screening based on title and abstract, 3 papers emerged as pertinent to the subject matter. These studies shed light on several critical findings.

In the 3 publications found, cost-effectiveness analyses for using PRS in breast cancer screening have been conducted, comparing several PRS strategies in varying countries. Wong et al., developed a Markov model to compare PRS-based breast cancer screening with the current biennial mammogram screening program in Singapore. High-risk individuals received an annual ultrasound or mammogram from age 35 – 74, intermediate-risk individuals received a biennial mammogram from age 40 – 74 and low-risk individuals received a triennial mammogram from age 40 – 74 [102]. Pashayan and colleagues adopted a life table modelling approach to compare PRS-based screening compared to current age-based screening and to a no-screening strategy in the UK. In the PRS strategy, women received PRS at age 50 and received additional screening every three years when the risk exceeded a defined risk threshold. Several different risk thresholds were included [103]. Mital and Nguyen constructed a decision tree/microsimulation model to compare eight screening strategies in a US setting. Strategies included no screening, annual screening for all, screening guided by AI risk prediction of index mammography at age 40, PRS at age 40, and family history stratified screening. The cost-effectiveness was calculated for low-risk individuals receiving no screening and for low-risk individuals receiving biennial mammograms [104].

All studies showed that risk tailored screening would be a cost-effective strategy compared to currently used screening programs. Wong et al. presented an incremental

cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER) of -3713.80 SGD/quality-adjusted life year (QALY), indicating that PRS-based screening would result in higher health benefits and lower costs in the Singaporean setting. PRS risk distributions were obtained from an unpublished study. Additionally, the model used risk multipliers for the PRS risk groups, which were assumption-based [102]. Pashayan, et al. showed that lowering the risk threshold for mammography resulted in a linear increase of screening costs. Considering a willingness to pay of £20,000 pounds per QALY gained, the PRS screening strategy with a 70th percentile risk threshold cutoff for triennial mammography led to the largest net monetary benefit. Compared to age-based screening, this strategy yielded 443 incremental QALYs and a reduction of costs with £537,985. The model used relative risks for breast cancer for the PRS risk groups, which were obtained from a theoretical modeling study [103]. In the study of Mital and Nguyen, AI-based risk screening was the most cost-effective strategy. It dominated PRS-based strategies (lower costs and more QALYs) due to the increased accuracy of AI in identifying high-risk women compared to PRS. Comparing the two PRS-based strategies (no screening for low risk or biennial screening for low risk), the no screening strategy led to more QALYs and lower costs. The effects of PRS on screening were incorporated through an AUC for breast cancer prediction obtained from a case-control study [104]. Finally, Mital and Nguyen, and Pashayan, et al. found that adopting a PRS strategy resulted in a higher number of breast cancer deaths. Contrarily, adopting PRS reduced the number of breast cancer deaths in the study by Wong, et al.

The cost-effectiveness analyses published so far examined different strategies in varying countries using other modeling techniques. However, the findings of the studies were comparable. All studies showed that tailored screening (PRS or AI-based screening) led to more QALYs, which could be achieved at lower costs than current non-tailored screening strategies. However, these gains were achieved at the downside of an increase in breast cancer deaths. This shows the trade off decision-makers face in implementing risk tailored screening techniques. These models show the trade off decision-makers face between the harms (number of over diagnoses, invasive screening methods) and benefits (lower number of cancer deaths) of different screening strategies. While the findings of the economic analyses were coherent, it must be noted that no randomized controlled trials were available to inform the models. Input estimates had to be obtained from different observational studies, which were described to have varying demographic and personal risk factors. Furthermore, the models assumed 100% attendance and compliance with screening and follow-up, which is unrealistic in the real world. While these studies show the potential of PRS to be cost-effective, more robust data is required to fully evaluate risk-tailored breast cancer screening.

4 Conclusion

This review examined the current state of polygenic risk scores (PRS) across various aspects including concerns, perspectives, analytical models and designs, transferability across ancestries, economic evaluations, and implementation.

4.1 Key Findings

- Communication is crucial for effective utilization of PRS in clinical settings. Clear communication strategies are necessary to ensure patients understand the complexities of PRS and can make informed decisions. Healthcare professionals need proper training and education to deliver accurate information about PRS limitations and benefits.
- PRS hold promise for various applications in preventive medicine, therapeutic decisions, and patient follow-up. However, challenges including accuracy in diverse ethnicities, appropriate selection methods, and translation into actionable clinical steps need to be addressed.
- Ethical and social implications of widespread PRS implementation require careful consideration. Cost-benefit analyses, reimbursement issues, and the psychological impact of knowing individual disease risks are important factors to address.
- Advancements in PRS design involve the integration of multi-omics data, machine learning algorithms, and environmental factors. This leads to more comprehensive risk assessment and personalized medicine approaches.
- Transferability of PRS across ancestries is a significant concern. PRS developed in European populations often have limited accuracy in other ethnicities. Large-scale GWAS studies in diverse populations are needed to improve the generalizability of PRS.
- Economic evaluations suggest that tailored screening strategies guided by PRS have the potential to be cost-effective compared to current practices. However, trade-offs exist between increased benefits and potential harms such as overdiagnosis.

4.2 Relevance and Added Value

This review provides a comprehensive overview of the current landscape of PRS research, highlighting its potential and limitations. By summarizing the ethical considerations, communication challenges, and design advancements, this work offers valuable insights for researchers, healthcare professionals, and policymakers involved in the development and implementation of PRS.

4.3 Limitations

This review is limited to the analysis of published studies retrieved from specific databases. Emerging research and unpublished data might not have been captured.

4.4 Future Directions

- Further research is needed to improve the accuracy and transferability of PRS across diverse populations.
- Studies investigating the long-term impact of PRS on patient behavior and healthcare utilization are warranted.
- Development of clear guidelines and regulations for the responsible use and communication of PRS in clinical settings is crucial.

- Continued research on integrating PRS with other clinical data and environmental factors to optimize risk prediction and personalized medicine strategies.

Overall, PRS are a rapidly evolving field with significant potential to revolutionize healthcare. By addressing the current limitations and ethical considerations, PRS can become a valuable tool for disease prevention, risk stratification, and personalized medicine.

Supplementary information. If your article has accompanying supplementary file/s please state so here.

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Appendix A Section title of first appendix

An appendix contains supplementary information that is not an essential part of the text itself but which may be helpful in providing a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem or it is information that is too cumbersome to be included in the body of the paper.

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